

Figure Z10

A

scWAT

Std. Diet

HFD

Sed Train

Sed Train

Bulk RNA-seq deconvolution
Relative proportion

- Adipocyte
- Adipose stem cell
- Smooth muscle cell
- Preadipocyte
- Vascular
- Epithelial cell
- Glial
- B
- NK
- T
- Macrophage
- Neutrophil

vWAT

Animal: 1 2 3 4 5 1 2 3 4 5 1 2 3 4 5 1 2 3 4 5

B **Skeletal Muscle**

Std. Diet

HFD

Sed Train

Sed Train

Animal: 1 2 3 4 5 1 2 3 4 5 1 2 3 4 5 1 2 3 4 5

- Fast_myonuclei
- Slow_myonuclei
- Tenocyte
- FAP
- Adipocyte
- Endothelial cell
- Macrophage

Figure Z10: Sample-specific deconvolution. (A and B) Relative cell-type proportions in each sample after deconvolving bulk RNA-seq data from two WAT depots (**A**) and skeletal muscle (**B**). Each bar is coloured by cell type.